

DESIGNING LONG-LASTING RUT-RESISTANT ASPHALT CONCRETE USING MARSHALL MIX DESIGN METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This paper summarizes the binder and wearing course mix design test results used during the sectional rehabilitation of the Tanzam highway in Tanzania. The mix design was carried out using the Marshall mix design procedures whereby the Marshall specimens were compacted to refusal using 500 Marshall blows. The optimum binder content was selected as the binder content, which gave 3% air voids at 500 blows - 0.4%. The rehabilitated pavement section has been heavily trafficked, with estimated traffic loading of 6 million equivalent standard axles traversing the pavement within three years with no noticeable rutting. Therefore, the Marshall mix design method can be used to design asphalt concrete for heavily loaded pavement if the binder content is correctly selected to limit the effect of post-construction densification.

INTRODUCTION

In 2018, the Ministry of Works of Tanzania introduced the interim mix design procedure for the bituminous pavement layers using SUPERPAVE[1]. The method is still uncommon for most contractors and consultants. Furthermore, the laboratory equipment for carrying out the mix design using SUPERPAVE procedures is not readily available in most laboratories. For projects designed before the introduction of the Superpave manual, their project specifications call for Marshall mix design procedures as outlined in MOW 2000 Standard Specifications for Road Works[2] for designing the bituminous pavement mixes.

Most hot Mix Asphalt [HMA] pavement structures in Tanzania, particularly those designed to carry more than 3 million equivalent standard axles [traffic loading of TLC 10¹ and above], have exhibited premature distress. Some of these asphalt pavement

structures showed signs of distress during the first year of trafficking, even though these pavement structures were designed to last for at least twenty years. It is also noted that the distress and/or premature failure in most cases is mainly confined to severe sites like climbing lanes [with a gradient of more than 4%], police checkpoints, superelevation, and area with speed humps. At these severe sites, the vehicles tend to slow down to a speed of less than 30 km/h. At this crawling speed, the loading time increases and becomes the influential factor in forming permanent deformation because it influences the cohesive resistance of the asphalt concrete. The bituminous binder is viscoelastic material and softens at higher temperatures and long loading times. Higher temperatures and long loading times allow considerable secondary compaction of the mix under traffic. Thus, the cohesive resistance increases at high vehicle speeds and low temperatures. At low vehicle speeds and high temperatures, the cohesive resistance decreases. The formation of permanent deformation is exacerbated because in Tanzania, particularly during hot sunny days, the asphalt in most parts tends to operate at a temperature of more than 60°C [1]. The temperature primarily affects the viscosity of the binder. At a temperature of more than 45°C, the binder softens considerably, and the shear resistance of the asphalt mix becomes highly dependent on the frictional resistance offered by the aggregates. Therefore, if the post-construction densification is underestimated during the mix design of the asphalt mixes, the mix could densify dangerously during trafficking to in-situ air voids of less than 3%, thereby making the asphalt mix prone to rutting [4]. The reduction in air void reduces the coarse aggregate's interparticle friction and mechanical interlock because the aggregate floats in the binder; thus, the traffic loading is transferred to the fine aggregate and bitumen matrix. This

¹ TLC 10 is a traffic loading class within the range of 3-10 million equivalent standard axle based on traffic loading classification as

provided in Tanzania Pavement and Materials Design Manual [3]

implies that if the asphalt concrete is not designed to be stiff enough to withstand the high stress imparted by heavy and overloaded vehicles, it will become over-compacted and deform plastically.

The Tanzam highway pavement exhibited severe rutting exceeding 15 mm. This rutting occurred in several sections along the alignment. The rutting were mainly confined in urban areas where heavy vehicles tend to slow down and also in locations with a steep gradient of more than 4%. The formation of rutting necessitated pavement rehabilitation using rut-resistant asphalt concrete mix.

This paper presents the Marshall mix design procedures used for designing a bituminous binder course and wearing course used during the sectional rehabilitation of the Tanzam highway. The bituminous pavement layers were placed in Kingolwira and Mikumi areas along the Tanzam highway. The Tanzam highway is the most heavily loaded pavement structure in Tanzania. The traffic count carried out in 2016 indicates that the average number of commercial vehicles traversing the pavement per day (ADT) was 6971. The pavement is designed to endure traffic loading of 37.835 million equivalent standard axles for 20 years [traffic loading category of TLC 50²]. The pavement layers are designed in accordance with Pavement and Material Design Manual [3], are made of 50 mm of bituminous wearing course, 200 mm of dense bitumen macadam, and 250 mm of cement-stabilized sub-base with minimum unconfined compressive strength of 0.5 MPa underlain with improved upper subgrade layers with minimum CBR value of more than 15.

RUTTING MEASUREMENT AND IN-SITU AIR VOIDS OF THE FAILED PAVEMENT

Figure 1 shows the rut-depth measured along Kingolwira and Mikumi sections. It can be seen that the rut depth in some locations is more than 15 mm, which, per MoW Pavement and Materials Design Manual, is classified as a warning. The air voids in the areas that exhibited plastic deformation and those that did not were determined. The determined air voids, along with other air voids data given in

ORN 19[4], are plotted in Figure 2, from which it can be seen that the air voids data collected in the Middle East, Malaysia, and East Africa as reported in ORN 19 shows that the probability of formation of plastic deformation increases when the air voids are less than 3. Air void data collected during this study shows the same trend.

The air voids data shown in Figure 2 were used to compute the probability of the formation of permanent deformation using a logistic model. The established logistic model is shown as equation 1.

$$P(x) = \frac{e^{(-4.172+1.504x)}}{1 + e^{(-4.172+1.504x)}} \dots (1)$$

Where

'x' is the air void

P(x) is the probability of NO plastic deformation

The probability of the formation of plastic deformation computed using the logistic model shown in equation 1 suggests that the critical air void at which the probability of plastic deformation is 0.5 is 2.78, which is very close to 3. The plot of the logistic model is shown in Figure 3. At 3% air voids, the probability of plastic deformation is 0.416, while at 4% air voids, the probability of plastic deformation is only 0.137.

Figure 1: Measured rut depth at Kingolowirwa and Mikumi section

² TLC 50 is a traffic loading class within the range of 20-50 million equivalent standard axle based on traffic loading classification as

provided in Tanzania Pavement and Materials Design Manual [3]

Figure 2: Occurrence of plastic deformation as a function of air voids (source ORN 19 and this study)

Figure 3: the probability of occurrence of plastic deformation based on the air void content

VOLUMETRIC DATA IN MoW 2000 SPECIFICATIONS

Section 4200 of the MOW General Specifications gives requirements for continuously graded asphalt concrete AC 20, AC 14, and AC 10 (the numerical value after the AC stands for nominal aggregate size). There are no volumetric requirements for dense bitumen macadam (DBM). The General Specification was drafted before introducing performance-graded binder specifications; therefore, bitumen specified for hot mixed asphalt is penetration grade complying with AASHTO M20. Table 4202/3 of the MOW 2000 specifications, produced herein as Table 1,

gives the specified volumetric parameters for the asphalt to be achieved during the asphalt mix design for the wearing course asphalt mix.

The MOW specification calls for the asphalt concrete to be designed following standard procedures outlined in the Central Materials Laboratory [CML] test No. 3.18 and 3.19[5]. The content of these procedures is identical to the old editions of Asphalt Institute Manual Series 2 (6th editions or lower). In accordance with these test procedures, the asphalt concrete mix design is carried out following the conventional Marshall mix design procedures whereby the briquettes are subjected to 75 blows of a Marshall hammer on each side. Thereafter, the volumetric parameters are computed. The optimum binder content is selected by averaging the binder content, which gives the maximum density and stability, and the binder content, which gives the median of the specified air voids. Since Table 4202/3 of the General specification gives the range of air voids as 3-6%, the binder content corresponding to air voids of 4.5% is usually taken. This optimum binder content is checked against other specified parameters, such as air voids, voids in mineral aggregates [VMA], and voids filled with binder [VFB], to ascertain the selected optimum binder content complies with the project specifications. Since the air voids dictate the performance of hot mix asphalt, the optimum binder content selection was modified in the Seventh Edition [2014] of MS 2. The optimum binder content in the new version of MS 2 is selected at the median of the specified air voids. Other parameters like VMA, stability, density, and flow are checked for compliance against the selected optimum binder content.

Based on the inspection of several bituminous pavement structures designed in accordance with the conventional Marshall mix design method as given in MoW 2000 specification and adopting an air void of 4.5% to select the binder content (the median of 3-6% specified in table 4203/3 of MoW specifications), it can be concluded that the procedures are not appropriate for designing an asphalt mix for heavily loaded pavement. The achievable density using the 75 Marshall blows and selecting the optimum binder content at the median of 3-6 air void does not represent the ultimate conditions and density in the road pavement after secondary compaction by slow-moving heavy vehicles.

Table 1: Volumetric parameters as given in MOW 2000 specifications Table 4203/3

Parameter	Specifications
Marshall flow [mm]	2-4
Marshall Stability [N]	Minimum 9000 for severely loaded area 8000-10000 for TLC 20-TLC50 7000-15000 for TLC 3-TLC10 4000-10000 for TLC 1 and lower
Air voids [%]	3-6
Voids in Mineral Aggregates [%]	Minimum 14 for AC 20 Minimum 15 for AC 14 Minimum 16 for AC 10
Requirement after refusal laboratory compaction [severely loaded areas only] ³	Air voids shall be a minimum of 3%
Indirect Tensile strength [kPa]	Minimum 800 tested at 25 °C
Immersion Index	75% Min ⁴

The specification calls for the asphalt mix to be compacted to refusal using a vibrating hammer method and retain at least 3% air voids at refusal density. Depending on the mix's compact-ability, in most cases, the 3% air void at refusal is far exceeding the maximum air void of 6% specified in the specifications. For some mixes, the air voids of 3% at refusal density correspond to more than 10% air voids at 75 Marshall blows. Figure 4 shows a dense bitumen mix used for remedial work of Malaba-Buguri project in Uganda. The air voids at 3%

³The specification provides that, the traffic loading class and whether requirements for severely loaded area will apply to any location shall be given in the drawings or special specification. Where such information is not given, the decision of the Engineer shall apply.

of the vibrating hammer corresponded to 10.7% at 75 Marshall blows[6]. This suggests that the specification of the maximum air void of 6 may conflict with the requirement of retaining at least 3% air voids at refusal density using the vibrating hammer method. The minimum air void of 3 is specified at 75 blows. It is practically impossible for any mix having 3% air voids at 75 blows to retain the same air voids when compacted using a vibrating hammer.

Figure 4: air voids versus binder content for the DBM mix used during remedial work of Malaba-Buguri in Uganda

MIX DESIGN

The primary aim of designing asphalt concrete is to ensure that the asphalt concrete will be durable, flexible, and rut-resistant. In Tanzania, the main failure criterion of the bituminous pavement is rutting due to post-construction densification and shear deformation of the asphalt mixes.

Therefore, the plastic deformation and formation of ruts are primarily due to an underestimate of secondary compaction that occurs under heavy traffic loads, which reduces the air void content to a critical level at which the plastic deformation occurs relatively rapidly, i.e., less than 3%. Therefore, the in-situ air voids are the most critical

⁴Erroneously the immersion Index limit is specified as 3-6 in MOW 2000 specification, normally the minimum specified immersion index is 75%

parameters that control the performance of asphalt concrete. The air void content attained after primary densification by traffic is an important design parameter since it is a key determinant of the resistance to shear deformation. The asphalt concrete must be designed to ensure that at least 3% of the air voids are retained during post-construction densification. In order to resist plastic deformation, asphalt mix depends mainly on internal friction between the aggregates particle. When voids are reduced to less than three, stresses are progressively transferred to the bitumen, forcing the aggregates apart and allowing the material to deform plastically. A well-designed asphalt mix would operate at air voids of about 4%, at which the shear resistance is expected to be optimal or satisfactory for traffic demand, and the probability of plastic deformation is only 14%. For well-designed mixes, the stability increases during trafficking due to aggregates' re-orientation and aging of the binder, preventing further densification of asphalt mat.

Therefore, the binder and wearing course mix design aimed to ensure that the designed mix would not dangerously densify to less than 3% air voids. During mix design, the mix was compacted using 75 Marshall blows, and its volumetric properties were evaluated. In accordance with project specifications, the post-construction densification was supposed to be assessed using a vibrating hammer. Owing to the fact that the vibrating hammer was not available on-site, the post-construction densification was evaluated by compacting the Marshall specimen using 500 blows. The air voids of the mix were further evaluated. The binder content, which yielded 3% air voids at 500 Marshall blows, was taken as the maximum binder content, at which, above it, the mix is likely to exhibit plastic deformation.

The dense bitumen macadam was designed using a maximum aggregate size of 40 mm, while the wearing course was designed using a maximum aggregate size of 20 mm. Performance grade binder PG64-16 was used for the production of both the binder and the wearing course. The durability of the mix and resistance to tensile strain at the bottom of the bituminous base depends on the amount of binder content. This was checked by computing the binder film thickness, which was found to be more than 7 microns, which is the

minimum film thickness recommended in ORN 19.

SELECTION OF OPTIMUM BINDER CONTENT

A well-designed asphalt mix is supposed to be rut-resistant; this is achieved by limiting the post-construction densification such that the mix stabilizes within the air voids range of 3-4 at which no further densification will be possible under traffic loading.

The selection of optimum binder content for the asphalt mix is the most critical since the quantity of the binder content largely dictates the performance of the mix. The achieved density using 500 Marshall blows can be regarded as adequate compaction at which no further compaction is likely to take place. However, data presented in Road Note 19 indicates that the refusal density carried out using a vibrating hammer gives a higher density than the one given by the 500 blows suggesting that the 500-blow density is not equivalent to the refusal density of the mix [4]. The summary of the compaction data at diverse compaction energy, as presented in Road Note 19, is shown in Figure 4, from which it can be seen that even 600 Marshall blows may not be equivalent to refusal density as determined using a vibrating hammer. The application of 500 Marshall blows does not portray the refusal reference density. Therefore, the selection of binder content at 3% air void using 500 Marshall blows may underestimate the post-construction densification of the asphalt concrete for a heavily loaded pavement structure. Therefore, the binder content, which gave 3% air voids at 500 blows, was regarded as the maximum binder content, at which, above it, the mix is likely to densify to less than 3% air voids. Since most asphalt plants operate at a binder variation of $\pm 0.3\%$, the optimum binder content was selected as the binder content, which yielded 3% air voids at 500 blows -0.4%. The 0.4% binder content reduction was taken to limit the possibility of exceeding the maximum binder content, which gives 3% air voids at 500 Marshall blows.

Figure 4: effect of compaction on mix properties (ORN 19)

BINDER COURSE MIX DESIGN

Four aggregate sizes, 0/6, 6/14, 14/20, and 20/37.5 mm, were used to produce the bound base. The gradings of individual aggregates and aggregate design structures used for the production of dense bitumen macadam (DBM 40) is shown in Figure 5. The relationship between air voids and binder content at 75 and 500 Marshall blows is shown in Figure 6. MoW 2000 Standard Specifications for Road Works does not specify the air void requirement for the binder course. The air voids in the binder course are required to allow for slight post-construction densification and slight binder thermal expansion without bleeding or losing stability. Furthermore, considering that the thickness of the wearing course is only 50mm, the binder course is also subjected to almost the same loading as that of the wearing course. Therefore, it can reasonably be postulated that the wearing course and binder course carry the imposed traffic load as one monolithic pavement layer. Therefore, the same procedure of selecting the optimum binder for both the binder and the wearing course was used. Therefore, based on the analysis of the air void at 500 blows, the optimum binder content for the binder course was 3.4% selected at 3.9% air void at 500 Marshall blows, corresponding to 6.7% air void at 75 Marshall blows, shown in Figure 6. The simulation of post-construction densification of the binder course is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 5: The hot bins grading and aggregate design structure for the binder course

Figure 6: Selection of optimum binder content for binder course

Figure 7: simulation of post-construction densification for the binder course

DESIGN OF BITUMINOUS WEARING COURSE

Four aggregate sizes, namely 0/3, 3/6, 6/10, and 10/20 mm aggregates, were used to produce the bituminous wearing course. The gradings of individual aggregates and aggregate design structures used to produce a bituminous wearing course (AC20) are shown in Figure 8.

Binder content yielded 3% air voids at 500 Marshall blows -0.4% was selected as the optimum binder content and was found to be 3.8%, corresponding to 4.3% air voids at 500 blows and 6.4% air voids at 75 blows.

Figure 8: The hot bins grading and aggregate design structure for the wearing course

Figure 9: Selection of optimum binder content for a bituminous wearing course

Figure 10: post construction densification simulation for the wearing course

QUALITY CONTROL OF VOLUMETRIC DATA DURING PRODUCTION

Asphalt samples were taken behind the paver during production for laboratory testing as part of the quality control. All specified parameters were tested, i.e., air voids, VMA, VFB, and Marshall stability. The air voids test results summary, which is the most critical performance indicator, is shown in Figures 11 for the binder course and 12 for the wearing course. The quality control of air void was based on the established air voids at 75 blows $\pm 1\%$, i.e., for the binder course, the air void was controlled within the range of $6.7 \pm 1\%$, while for the wearing course, the air voids were controlled within the range of $6.4 \pm 1\%$.

Figure 11: air void for binder course (at 75 blows)

Figure 12: air voids for wearing course at 75 blows

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Simulating the post-construction densification of the asphalt mix is an important method of checking the performance of the asphalt mix. Simulation of the post-construction densification using 500 blows as used during the mix design process gives an insight into whether the mix is likely to dangerously density to air voids of less than 3.

Based on the performance evaluation of the mixes presented in this study, it can be concluded that in the absence of more sophisticated equipment for designing asphalt mix using SUPERPAVE procedures, the mix can be designed using the conventional Marshal mix design procedure. The optimum binder content shall be selected at a binder content that gives 3% air voids at 500 blows -0.4%. The selected optimum content binder thickness shall be more than 7 μmm in line with the recommendation given in ORN 19 to ensure the durability of the asphalt mix.

REFERENCES:

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